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TEACHING AND LEARNING TECHNICAL AND MANAGERIAL LEADERSHIP SKILLS THROUGH SCENARIO-BASED LEARNING

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ABSTRACT

Today's scientists, engineers, and researchers, through traditional educational programs, have developed deep technical, analytical, and problem-solving skills. However, many lack the leadership, people management, knowledge transfer, and communication skills needed to be successful leaders. To fill this gap, MIT Open Learning along with faculty from MIT Sloan Management, the School of Engineering, and the Gordon Engineering Leadership Program developed the "Leadership Academy for Scientists, Engineers, and Researchers" (LASER). To successfully lead change within an organization, this audience needs a proven framework to fully understand organizational change. LASER utilizes an MIT framework known as the "Three Lenses" that provides three perspectives (strategic design, political, and cultural) to determine what data is being perceived in an organization, how to interpret the data, and how to view problems from multiple angles. The Three Lenses was chosen due to its ability to be transferable from an online classroom to the job site.

LASER's pedagogical model focuses on five types of educational activities: assess, explore, practice, apply, and share. The core of the learning material developed for LASER was built around the premise of transferrable skills and application in the real-world. To make the real-world context come to life, the delivery of the course content utilizes several strategies, one being the concept of scenario-based learning (SBL). SBL provides learners the ability to practice using what they have learned and applying it to a real-world scenario of a problem they are likely to encounter. This paper will further elaborate on this concept and provide examples.

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1 INTRODUCTION

Today's scientists, engineers, and researchers, through traditional educational programs, have developed deep technical, analytical, and problem-solving skills. However, many lack the leadership capabilities (people management, knowledge transfer, and communication skills) critical for success [1, 2, 3]. In technical professions, leaders need different skills to thrive. According to Grenny & Maxfield (2016) "The tech industry's combination of high-velocity competition, complexity, global talent, and interdependence among rivals makes it a truly unique environment, requiring a distinct set of leadership skills" [4]. To this end, a business unit within the Massachusetts Institute of Technology (MIT) called, "MIT xPRO" sought to address this need by developing a new online leadership program for the technical professional. This program became known as the Leadership Academic for Scientists, Engineers, and Researchers (LASER).

1.1 What Gaps Are Being Filled

LASER was a historic cross-Institute collaboration between the MIT Open Learning Office, faculty from MIT Sloan Management, the School of Engineering, and the Gordon Engineering Leadership Program leadership, bringing forth multiple experiences from MIT. LASER was designed uniquely in the sense that the content was created for a technical audience. From first time managers, individual contributors, and mid-level managers, anyone in this audience will find content relevant to their position. While most technical professionals have been trained to develop their hard skills, LASER focused on human skills. Human skills can be defined as "non-technical skills and attributes, which will be immune from machine replacement for the longest and will equip humans to thrive" [5]. According to Westerman & Stump (2020), "Digital and technical skills are critical to emerging jobs and industries, but it is the uniquely human skills that will be immune from machine replacement for the longest and will ensure individuals can thrive in the new economy" [5]. These human skills included growth mindset, critical thinking, collaboration, self-awareness, and negotiation among other skills. These skills were all necessary to include with the purpose of giving technical leaders the tools to become change agents. With these human skills in mind, LASER provided an opportunity for early and mid-career technical professionals to further develop their competencies as leaders in the workforce.

1.2 Three Lenses

For technical leaders to develop a strong skill set and to lead change effectively, being able to understand multiple perspectives is paramount. To aid in the understanding of perspectives, a framework from MIT's Sloan School of Management was selected called, "The Three Perspectives." This framework provided three perspectives on organizations, problems, and change efforts. The three perspectives or lenses, are known as the strategic design lens, the political lens, and the cultural lens [6]. Each of these lenses were important to navigate the dynamics of the formal side of organizations, to navigate the dynamics of the people

with relationships, power, and influence, and to navigate the dynamics of the cultural side.

LASER comprised of four online courses with the first three focused on one particular lens. The first 4-weeks course, “Understanding Organizational Strategy and Capabilities,” focused on the strategic design lens and designing organizations to achieve certain outcomes through a better understanding of the organizational mission, purpose and goals. These components are crucial to planning purposes and provide alignment to important measures of performance such as effectiveness and efficiency. The second 3-weeks course, “Negotiating and Applying Influence and Power,” was designed to focus on the social context and relational side of an organization. The outcomes from this course were to understand conflict and how to gain cooperation from individuals and groups within an organization. The third 3-weeks course on the cultural lens was titled, “Leading Change in Organizations.” This course was designed to leverage and navigate cultures and networks within an organization at any level.

After experiencing the three courses, learners transitioned to the final 3-weeks course in the online program called, “Discovering and Implementing Your Leadership Strengths.” This course transitioned the mindset and the learning experience of looking through different lenses to focusing on the inner self. Learners in this course discovered and analyzed their leadership traits and experienced visioning exercises to profile their own styles of being a leader and a change agent.

1.3 Pedagogical Model

In order to deliver the best learning experience, the LASER Program utilized a pedagogical model based on research from evidenced-based instructional design practices, learning sciences, and neuroscience. The design vision of the LASER curriculum, pedagogy, and learning environment is based in the latest neuroscience and cognitive behavioral science on learning, as well as best practices from decades of MIT’s pioneering work in digital learning [1]. Collaborating with faculty researchers in the MIT Integrated Learning Initiative (MITili), LASER puts evidence-based insight into action, implementing such digital learning innovations as modular content, interleaved assessments, visualizations and simulations, and interactive, online tutors with adaptive hinting and rapid feedback. This model contained five different elements of learning with exploring, practicing, applying, sharing, and assessing.

These principles followed MIT’s *mens et manus* motto, meaning mind and hand. Just as MIT’s founders were promoting education for practical application, LASER followed the same path as each course focused on teaching tangible real-world skills, their applications, and how they would transition to the workplace. To acquire a significant amount of knowledge within the duration of the online program, learners experienced hands-on activities and real-world applications which were established as the fundamentals for the learning process. Learners were expected to devote about 12 hours of work per course (3-4 hours per week). The elements of learning, considering our pedagogical model [7, 8, 9, 10], were segmented into:

- Explore: Students learn core concepts through watching engaging videos and reading research-based papers and articles.
- Practice: Through multiple choice questions, scenarios, and simulation activities, students practice concepts without an impact to their grade.
- Apply: Via case studies, essays, and self-reflection, students apply conceptual material to solve problems and take stock on how principles apply to their jobs.
- Share: Through peer-to-peer discussions and surveys/polls, students reflect on what they have learned, comment on other students' experiences and expand their knowledge through others' insights.
- Assess: Using pre- and post-assessments, peer assessment tools, as well as summative assessment instruments, students are evaluated on their understanding of the material and their ability to apply it to the workplace.

Figure 1: LASER Pedagogical Model

By following these learning practices, LASER leveraged MIT's wealth of knowledge and experience in the engineering, entrepreneurial, and leadership spaces, as well as its advanced approach to online learning.

1.4 Scenario-Based Learning

To create an effective and optimal learning experience for real-world applications, this program's curriculum was designed using a learning technique known as, "Scenario-Based Learning" [11]. Scenario-Based Learning or SBL, uses hypothetical or real-life scenarios to support active learning strategies. These were based upon the mentioned case studies throughout the program and involved learners imagining themselves in the scenario. By going through this process, learners needed to use critical thinking and decision-making skills throughout each part of the required problem. Learners were also able to practice and apply these skills in a safe environment where learning from mistakes and sharing their

experiences with other learners was encouraged. SBL was selected for this program due to the need for technical leaders to be able to apply the learned tangible skills in the workforce.

In order to create effective scenarios, these scenarios were developed by the course team visualizing themselves as being in the position of the learners. Scenarios could be practiced safely within the program's content and aided in the learning of the transferable skills. Problems were drafted based upon the program's curriculum, articles, and videos. Once the scenarios were designed, subject matter experts and faculty members were consulted for their relevancies to a technical professional. To verify their accuracy, the course team had the opportunity to speak to learners from different industries who completed a pilot run of the program. Both quantitative and qualitative methods were utilized to collect, analyze, and apply learner feedback.

1.5 SBL Examples

The following are several examples of the SBL problem types from LASER's curriculum. The first is from Understanding Organizational Strategies and Capabilities. In this example, learners have been introduced to a problem many organizations face called, "The Capability Trap" [12]. This problem revolves around organizations struggling with being able to implement a new idea. Based upon this information a scenario was created with an organization trying to adopt a new project management software, but were facing several challenges with the implementation process. The problem is presented as a package which included directions, a hypothetical email sent by the organization's human resources department, and the challenge the learner is supposed to solve. For this scenario, learners read this prompt:

"Imagine working for a manufacturer who specializes in futuristic technology. After months of research, your human resources department has concluded that a new type of project management software needs to be implemented company wide. The first time you heard of this research was only a few days ago and you haven't been informed of how this new project management software will be more efficient than your current one. The slow research process went over its expected amount of time and now, HR has quickly scheduled numerous training sessions on your calendar that overlap your weekly scheduled meetings. After a week goes by, you received an email containing a broad message about how and why this software was chosen, with a note at the bottom mentioning how correct utilization of this software will be included on your upcoming performance evaluation."

This message was then followed by an email acting as the HR representative from the prompt:

New Software Launch

Human Resources Department <message@hr.com>

Luke Hobson

Saturday, February 2, 2019 at 8:01 AM

[Show Details](#)

Good afternoon,

We are excited to announce that after careful consideration, we will be utilizing Ira as our new project management software! Due to time restrictions, we have already scheduled training sessions for each supervisor. These training sessions are *mandatory*. After these sessions have concluded, it is expected for Ira to be on all performance evaluations moving forwards.

Please contact us if you have any questions.

Thank you,

Luke Hobson, Ed.D
AVP, Talent Engagement
Human Resources

Figure 2: SBL Email

This example had learners use critical thinking skills to predict the outcome of this process. A reflection question was also asked following this SBL example to have the learners think about their own organization. The reflection question in this example ask learners asked, “Identify at least one example of the capability trap within your organization. Knowing what you know now, how would you approach this problem?”

Another example can be seen in the Discovering and Implementing Your Leadership Strengths course. Learners performed a personality test to better understand who they are as leaders. Learners are presented with the case of a company attempting to launch a new product facing various issues (production challenges, issues with the Director of Operations, Issues with the Head of Regulatory Affairs, and Issues with on-boarding influencers) and need to act as one of the roles of the scenario (a new employee recently promoted as general manager). After reading the case, learners were asked to share their answers on a discussion platform thread:

Figure 3: SBL Discussion Platform Thread

By using critical thinking skills and applying the course content, learners had to decide what actions to implement to successfully resolve the situation. This scenario also had learners relate to their personality traits scores, analyze why they would act in that direction, and how their traits impacted their leadership style.

2 CONCLUSION

To further develop tomorrow's technical leaders, MIT Open Learning and other business units within MIT designed the Leadership Academy for Scientists, Engineers, and Researchers (LASER). Learners of this program were supplied with the Three Lenses framework to assist with leading change within an organization. This framework provided perspectives on strategy, politics, and culture to understand organizational change and focused on transferable skills from the online classroom to the job site. LASER's pedagogical model focuses on five types of educational activities: assess, explore, practice, apply, and share. The delivery of the program's content utilized several strategies for effective online learning with scenario-based learning (SBL) in particular, being highlighted. SBL provided learners the ability to practice using what they learned and apply those skills to real-world scenarios of a problem.

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